

Hands-on Programming Session #2: Sorting Algorithms

During the hands-on programming session, you will use `LabSorting.java` skeleton file.

Exercise 1 Implement bubble sort.

Exercise 2 Implement insertion sort. Insertion sort will sort the array in-place.